

Synthesis of Possible Antifertility Compounds: Part III* Synthesis of 2,3-Diphenylbenzofurans

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Oxygenated 2,3-diphenyl-6-hydroxybenzofurans, their basic ethers and other derivatives have been prepared with a view to testing their antifertility activity.

Among the series of cyclic triaryl ethylene derivatives,¹⁻⁴ some 2,3-diphenyl benzofurans⁵ have antifertility activity and related biological properties. Further studies on 2,3-diphenyl benzofurans were therefore undertaken and compounds were prepared with oxygenated phenyl rings in addition to aminoalkoxy groups, in view of the presence of antifertility activity⁵⁻⁶ in basic ethers of compounds related to synthetic oestrogens having para alkoxy triphenyl ethylene structure such as (I). In the present series the following type (II) of compounds have been prepared.

The benzofurans were prepared by condensing appropriate benzoin and resorcinol by modification of the method of Brown *et al.*⁷ The basic ethers were obtained by condensing the benzofurans with amino ethyl chloride hydrochlorides.

EXPERIMENTAL

2,3, (p,p-dimethoxy) diphenyl-6-hydroxybenzofuran, colourless needles, m.p. 138° (Brown⁷ reports m.p. 136-7°). was used.

*Part I. Tiwari & Srivastava, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 445.

Part II, Tiwari and Srivastava, *This Journal*, in press.

1. Lednicer *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1955, 8, 52.
2. (a) Lednicer *et al.*, *Chem. Ind.*, 1963, 408.
(b) Benze *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 213.
(c) Benze *et al.*, *Experientia*, 1965, 21, 261.
(d) Lednicer *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, 9, 172.
3. Lednicer *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1965, 8, 725.
4. Grover *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1965, 8, 720.
5. Segal and Nelson, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1958, 98, 431.
6. Holtkamp *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, 105, 197.
7. Brown *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4305.

TABLE I
Structures II

R	R ₁	R ₂	M.P.°	%yield	Formula	%Carbon		%Hydrogen		%Nitrogen	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
C ₆ H ₅ CO	p-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	p-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	68°	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ O ₃	77.1	77.99	4.62	4.88	—	—
Cl ₄ CHCO	"	"	60°	85	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ Cl ₄	62.3	63.03	3.7	3.93	—	—
p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ N	"	"	144°	95	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	—	—	—	—	3.05	2.91
(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ .HCl	"	"	151-2°	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.86	2.90
CH ₂ CH ₂ N 	"	"	160-1°	92	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.71	2.83
CH ₂ CH ₂ N 	"	"	170°	88	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.56	2.82
C ₆ H ₅ CO	O.OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	p-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	64°	92	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ O ₅	77.2	77.99	4.59	4.88	—	—
Cl ₄ CHCO	"	"	64-5°	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₅ Cl ₄	62.16	63.03	3.8	3.93	—	—
p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ Cl ₄ CH ₂ N	"	"	140°	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₅ N	—	—	—	—	2.75	2.91
(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ .HCl	"	"	181°	86	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.80	2.90
CH ₂ CH ₂ N 	"	"	160°	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.74	2.82
CH ₂ CH ₂ N 	"	"	167°	91	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.80	2.82

TABLE I (contd.)

Structure II

R	R ₁	R ₂	M.P.*	% Yield	Formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
CH ₂ CH ₂ N (C ₆ H ₅) ₂ HCl	3:4 (O-CH ₂ -O) C ₆ H ₅	3:4 (O-CH ₂ -O) C ₆ H ₅	240°	84	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.60	2.74
CH ₂ CH ₂ N		"	250°	87	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.53	2.68
CH ₂ CH ₂ N		"	253-54°	88	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	—	—	—	—	2.58	2.67

*All the M. P. s. are uncorrected.

2-(p-Methoxy) phenyl-3-(o-methoxy) phenyl-6-hydroxy-benzofuran.—2,4 dimethoxybenzoic acid (0.02 M), resorcinol (0.03 M), and peroxide free dioxan (20 ml) and conc. HCl (10 ml) were refluxed for 8 hr. and then poured into water. The oily layer which separated was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was extracted with 8% sodium hydroxide solution and the aqueous solution was acidified. The oily material which separated was taken up in ether, which was diluted with sufficient petroleum (60-80°) to precipitate out the oil. Granular crystals separated out from the oil when it was kept for some time. Recrystallisation from petroleum-ether mixture gave colourless needles, m.p. 133°, yield 4.5 g. (66.2%). (Found: C, 75.8; H, 5.53; $C_{22}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 76.3; H, 5.2%).

2,3-Bis-3:4-methylenedioxydiphenyl-6-hydroxybenzofuran.—Piperoin (0.01 M); resorcinol (0.04 M), peroxide-free dioxan (20 ml) and conc. HCl (10 ml) were refluxed at 110-115° for 8 hr. The extraction of hydroxybenzofuran was carried out with 2% sodium hydroxide solution. The brownish semisolid obtained on working up the reaction mixture, was extracted with hot ether-petroleum mixture (20:80) several times, colourless needles appeared after keeping the extract overnight which was recrystallised from the same solvent mixture, and had m.p. 217°, yield 0.9 g. (24%). (Found: C, 70.1; H, 3.46; $C_{22}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 70.58; H, 3.74%).

Dialkyl Aminosthyl Ethers.—A mixture of the appropriate dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride (0.001M), hydroxy benzofuran (0.001M), freshly ignited potassium carbonate (1 g.), and acetone (25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 24 hr. After removal of acetone, the mixture was shaken with water, and syrupy solid which separated out was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with dil. alkali, water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and dry HCl passed into the solution. Solid hydrochloride which separated out was recrystallised from absolute ethanol.

The *p*-nitrobenzyl ethers of the benzofurans were prepared by refluxing *p*-nitrobenzyl chloride and hydroxy benzofuran in equivalent quantities in acetone, in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate for 16 hr. The ethers were recrystallised from acetone-methanol mixture.

The benzoyl and dichloroacetyl ethers of benzofurans were prepared in alkaline solution and recrystallised from ethanol.

The yield, m.p. and analyses of the derivatives are recorded in Table I.

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